

Thrombocytopenia in Hypertensive Disorders of Pregnancy

Manmohan Krishna Pandey¹, Purnima Mitra Pandey²

¹Professor, Department of Medicine, Autonomous State Medical College, Gonda, Uttar Pradesh, India

²Associate Professor, Department of Pathology, Autonomous State Medical College, Gonda, Uttar Pradesh, India.

ABSTRACT

Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy (HDP) are major contributors to maternal and neonatal morbidity worldwide¹. Thrombocytopenia (<150,000/ μ L) is a common hematological abnormality in HDP². Objectives: Estimate the incidence of thrombocytopenia in HDP and analyze maternal and perinatal outcomes according to severity. Materials and Methods: Prospective observational study of 67 pregnant women with HDP and thrombocytopenia over 18 months. Data on demographics, platelet counts, severity of HDP, maternal complications, and perinatal outcomes were collected. Results: Mild thrombocytopenia: 18 (27%), moderate: 37 (55%), severe: 12 (18%). HDP distribution: preeclampsia non-severe 15 (22%), preeclampsia severe 32 (48%), eclampsia 10 (15%), gestational hypertension 10 (15%). Poor maternal outcomes in 12 patients (18%), two maternal deaths in severe thrombocytopenia. Maternal outcomes significantly associated with severity ($p=0.021$). Perinatal outcomes worse in severe thrombocytopenia ($p=0.035$). Conclusion: Thrombocytopenia in HDP increases maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality. Early monitoring and intervention are recommended.

Keywords: Thrombocytopenia, Preeclampsia, Eclampsia, HDP (hypertensive disorders of pregnancy).

INTRODUCTION

Hypertensive disorders in pregnancy (HDP) are conditions that involve high blood pressure during gestation, including gestational hypertension (high blood pressure after 20 weeks without other symptoms), pre-eclampsia (high blood pressure with organ damage, like protein in the urine, after 20 weeks), chronic hypertension (existing high blood pressure before pregnancy), and pre-eclampsia superimposed on chronic hypertension. Eclampsia is pre-eclampsia with seizures, and HELLP syndrome is hemolysis, elevated liver enzymes, and low platelets.³ Preeclampsia occurs in 5–10% of pregnancies⁴ and eclampsia is characterized by seizures in preeclampsia⁵. Thrombocytopenia (<150,000/ μ L) is common in HDP, due to physiological (hemodilution) or pathological causes (HELLP, acute fatty liver)^{6,7}. It is associated with postpartum hemorrhage, DIC, abruption, maternal mortality⁸, and IUFD, early neonatal death⁹. Early

identification and monitoring can reduce complications¹⁰. Multiple studies are available regarding this condition in developed and developing countries but few studies are for rural India in tarai belt. Almost no study is available for Gonda region of Uttar Pradesh. The study was planned to know the extent of burden in the society so that community awareness and concerned health programming can be done.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- Study design: Prospective observational study.
- Duration: 18 months
- Setting: Dept. of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Tertiary Care Centre, Gonda

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

- Participants: 67 pregnant women with HDP and thrombocytopenia
- Inclusion: ≥ 20 weeks gestation, platelet $< 150,000/\mu\text{L}$
- Exclusion: pre-existing thrombocytopenia, autoimmune, hematologic disease, infectious disease (Dengue, Malaria, Scrub typhus, Chikangunya, Typhoid)
- Data collected: Demographics, platelet counts, HDP severity, maternal and perinatal outcomes.
- Thrombocytopenia classification: Mild (100,000–150,000/ μL), Moderate (50,000–99,000/ μL), Severe ($< 50,000/\mu\text{L}$)
- Statistical analysis: Chi-square test; $p < 0.05$ significant

RESULTS

Table 1: Distribution of HDP in 67 patients

Disorder	Number (%)
Pre-eclampsia non-severe	15 (22%)
Preeclampsia severe	32 (48%)
Eclampsia	10 (15%)
Gestational hypertension	10 (15%)

Table 2: Severity of thrombocytopenia

Severity	Number (%)
Mild	18 (27%)
Moderate	37 (55%)
Severe	12 (18%)

Maternal outcomes: 12 patients (18%) had poor outcomes: postpartum hemorrhage 5, DIC 3, abruption 2, maternal deaths 2 (severe). Maternal outcomes associated with severity ($p=0.021$). Perinatal outcomes: IUFD 10 (15%), early neonatal deaths 8 (12%), higher in severe thrombocytopenia. Association significant ($p=0.035$).

DISCUSSION

Thrombocytopenia is frequent in HDP; moderate most common. Severe thrombocytopenia correlates with poor maternal and perinatal outcomes. Maternal complications include postpartum hemorrhage, DIC, abruption, and maternal deaths¹¹. IUFD and early neonatal deaths are higher in severe thrombocytopenia¹². Early identification, routine monitoring, and multidisciplinary care improve outcomes¹³.

Management and treatment:

Monitoring: Close monitoring of blood pressure and other symptoms in pregnancy and after delivery.

Medication: Blood pressure medication is prescribed if it is more than 140/90 mmHg to prevent complications like stroke.

Hospitalization: Hospitalization is necessary for severe cases to monitor the mother and baby and manage blood pressure.

Delivery: Delivery is the only cure for pre-eclampsia.

Preventative measures: Women at high risk of pre-eclampsia may be advised to take a daily low-dose aspirin.

CONCLUSION

Thrombocytopenia in HDP is associated with increased maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality. Regular platelet monitoring, early recognition, and timely multidisciplinary management are essential.

REFERENCES

1. Cunningham FG, Leveno KJ, Bloom SL, et al. *Williams Obstetrics*. 25th ed. McGraw-Hill; 2018.
2. Sibai BM. Thrombocytopenia in pregnancy. *N Engl J Med*. 2013;369:1260–1261.
3. Roberts JM, Cooper DW. Pathogenesis and genetics of pre-eclampsia. *Lancet*. 2001;357:53–56.
4. ACOG Practice Bulletin No. 222, Hypertension in pregnancy, 2020.
5. Duley L. The global impact of pre-eclampsia and eclampsia. *Semin Perinatol*. 2009;33:130–137.
6. Sainio S, Kekomäki R, Teramo K. Thrombocytopenia in pregnancy. *Acta Obstet Gynecol Scand*. 2000;79:59–63.
7. George JN, et al. Thrombocytopenia in pregnancy: HELLP syndrome and related disorders. *Blood Rev*. 2012;26:157–164.
8. Audibert F, et al. Maternal outcome in pregnancy-related thrombocytopenia. *Am J Obstet Gynecol*. 2000;183:445–451.
9. Martin JN, et al. Perinatal outcome in severe thrombocytopenia. *Obstet Gynecol*. 2003;101:1015–1020.
10. Contreras C, et al. Management of thrombocytopenia in hypertensive disorders. *J Maternal Fetal Neonatal Med*. 2010;23:1154–1159.
11. Roberts CL, et al. Severe maternal morbidity in hypertensive disorders. *BMJ*. 2005;331:1195–1199.
12. Rana S, et al. Maternal and fetal outcomes in thrombocytopenia. *Hypertension*. 2014;63:150–156.
13. Knight M, et al. Multidisciplinary care for high-risk pregnancies. *Lancet*. 2016;387:1031–1043.

HOW TO CITE: Manmohan Krishna Pandey, Purnima Mittra Pandey, Thrombocytopenia in Hypertensive Disorders of Pregnancy, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, 1 (12), 834-836. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17938684>

